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Collaboration of General Education and Special Education Teachers During Emergency Remote Teaching: Challenges and Opportunities

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Abstract: This study is centered on the concepts of collaborative teaching and how it is utilized by both General Education and Special Education teachers in handling children with special needs during the time of emergency remote teaching. Collaborative Teaching is an approach that consists of both General and Special Education teachers working hand in hand to effectively teach children with special needs. This study aims to identify the challenges and opportunities experienced by both General Education and Special Education teachers in using the collaborative teaching approach in teaching and handling children with special needs during the period of emergency remote teaching. The output and significance of this study are to prepare and provide teachers with teaching strategies that surround the concept of utilizing collaborative teaching to accommodate, support, and teach children with special needs should the need to return to the state of emergency remote teaching occur in the future. This study utilizes the phenomenological research design since the goal of this research is to examine the phenomenon of the General Education and Special Education teachers' experience with using collaborative teaching in handling children with special needs during emergency remote teaching. The results of this study include emerging challenges in collaborative teaching that both General and Special Education teachers experienced, including the following barriers: unstable internet connection, lack of confidence and cooperation, inadequate support, limited time constraints, and conflicts in schedule. On the other hand, the opportunities that they experienced include the following: enhanced communication, enhanced sharing of teaching strategies, training, and provision of various techniques that can aid and improve the approach for collaborative teaching.

Keywords: *collaborative teaching, gen ed teachers, sped teachers, children with special needs, emergency remote teaching*

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic significantly impacted the various practices of SpEd teachers and parents in handling children with special needs, which was different from how their

practices in the traditional classroom (Lange, 2021). In the traditional education system, online education allows students and teachers flexible access to teaching and learning. Due to the pandemic, traditional classes shifted to distance learning at all levels of education; it is called Emergency Remote Teaching (ERT). Emergency remote teaching was brought up during the pandemic as a provisional teaching solution to the emerging crisis (Misirli & Ergulec, 2021). During the pandemic, emergency remote teaching significantly altered how a SpEd teacher handled children with special needs (CSN), negating the special feature of SpEd programs (Nelson, 2020). As the 2019-2020 school year ended and the 2020-2021 school year began, the pandemic significantly impacted one of the most at-risk groups of learners—children with special needs (CSN).

The ERT has posed a persistent problem, particularly for CSNs, whose voices are unheard of in normal times and whose problems were only intensified during the emergency. During the pandemic, government measures must include CSNs who have universal rights, as no one should be left behind in this uncertain crisis (Toquero, 2020a). Consequently, CSNs also endure many issues on top of the scarcity of the required health care during the pandemic (Toquero, 2020b).

Collaboration is an approach that allows two or more educators and specialists to come together to contribute their individual skills to develop a mutual understanding of expertise (Mofield, 2020). In the context of SpEd, one article explained that collaboration of SpEd teams could include Gen Ed instructors, speech-language pathologists, SpEd teachers, occupational therapists, school psychologists, and social workers, among others, in order to enhance the development of CSNs (Coughlin, 2017a). In this study, collaboration includes one Gen Ed teacher and one SpEd teacher; when combined, they produced constructive teaching strategies. The collaboration aimed to help CSNs achieve their learning needs through a Gen Ed curriculum while attending a SpEd program (Flores, 2020). Communication and collaboration among teachers are considered to have a significant impact on the success of inclusivity and meeting the educational needs of diverse learners (Hiller, 2019).

The foundation of this study lies in the social constructivism learning theories and works of Lev Vygotsky, which gave rise to new literature about collaboration. Drucker (1999), John-Steiner (1992; 1998), Moran and John-Steiner (2003), and Kramer and Gray (1989) opined that utilizing a social constructivist view in the realm of education can enable teachers to construct new ideas to enhance their instruction (as cited in Fulton, 2003). The foundational work of Vygotsky (1978) emphasized that collaboration can be utilized to build knowledge between individuals and that individuals learn through social interactions and engagements in generating knowledge and enhancing learning (Moran & John-Steiner, 2003). Additionally, Moran and John-Steiner (2003) discussed that in utilizing the Vygotskian framework, mental functions are effectively experienced in social settings, and learnings can be accessed and generated through social interaction. Moreover, Lincoln and Guba (1985) stated that ideas and knowledge are generated through collaboration wherein relationships, the environment, and context play a vital role.

The significance of this study lies in its contribution to further explore the experiences of teachers, more specifically in solving challenges and enhancing opportunities in handling children with special needs using collaborative teaching. The study also provides information about emergency remote teaching in the Philippines. This research mainly offers answers to these questions: What are the perceptions of in-service Gen Ed

and SpEd teachers about teaching collaboration to meet the needs of children with special needs during emergency remote teaching? What challenges in collaborative teaching have Gen Ed and SpEd teachers experienced in handling children with special needs in an emergency remote teaching setting? What opportunities did the Gen Ed and SpEd teachers encounter to overcome the challenges they experienced in collaborative teaching in handling children with special needs during emergency remote teaching? This study would serve as an additional guide for future teachers and researchers to prepare them for the future, particularly during future pandemics.

Collaborative Teaching

Collaborative teaching is a type of interaction or communication wherein two or more teachers that have common objectives work together (Ricci & Fingon, 2017). In Special Education, collaborative teaching involves different kinds of professionals, including General Education teachers, Special Education teachers, speech-language pathologists, therapists, psychologists, and social workers who actively collaborate to enhance the development of children with special needs (Coughlin, 2017b).

Likewise, the collaboration of Gen Ed teachers and SpEd teachers is essential in attaining the needs of every school in handling CSN as they are included in regular education classrooms and molded for a better future. Many school districts have implemented an inclusion model or models in which Gen Ed and SpEd teachers collaborate to ensure that all children make progress (Daniels, 2017). As such, Hargreaves (1994) stipulates that using CT improves a teacher's productivity and professional development, raises responsibility in the workplace, creates learning opportunities for instructors, provides insight and reflection on the practice of education, and reduces the teachers' workload. However, this claim was contested by Jonson (2003), who explained that CT could intensify work, make educators lose autonomy in teaching, inflict conflicts with other colleagues, and create a sense of factionalism. Additionally, Hargreaves also stated that using CT can provide significant drawbacks for the teachers, such as CT can be needless and useless, making teachers inefficient in teaching their students.

Nevertheless, authors such as Achinstein (2002), Chan and Pang (2006), and Clement and Vanderbeghe (2000) all agreed with Hargreaves' claim; they explained that CT could be beneficial because it provides educators with the opportunity to establish healthy relationships with their peers, which they can utilize to their advantage by sharing insights and experiences, evaluating their teaching instruction so that they can improve, and collaborating to produce necessary learnings.

However, one study by Ferri et al. (2020) asserted that during the time of the pandemic, emergency remote teaching could bring challenges that can affect the educational models of the students in utilizing technology for their learning process. Specifically, technological challenges, pedagogical challenges, social challenges, and even the teacher's use of collaborative teaching can become a problem for both the student and the teacher.

Emergency Remote Teaching

Emergency Remote Teaching is an alternative model for learning and teaching processes; thus, it is considered a feasible component in providing instructional support for students during the pandemic (Cahapay & Rotas, 2020). One study explained that ERT

is a term to describe the provision and delivery of instruction and learning during times of crisis. ERT promotes academic freedom by allowing teachers to design strategies depending on the current scenario to optimize students' learning despite their difficult situation (Toquero, 2020). In traditional education, it is defined as learning imparted through interactions when students and teachers meet face-to-face (Nabi, 2020).

Under challenging circumstances, desperate measures are required, and ERT can facilitate collaboration and the exchange of ideas and best practices among practitioners, educators, and researchers (Toquero, 2020). However, one study suggests that universities with face-to-face classes generally have the advantage of providing support to students, such as positive student reinforcement. Furthermore, the lack of social communication in an online class setting makes it significantly more challenging for students to communicate with each other than in face-to-face classes (Després-Bedward et al., 2018). Additionally, some students may struggle with online discourses due to their reliance on face-to-face interaction; most students are foreign to the concepts of the online learning environment, which can hinder their communication in an online channel (Després-Bedward et al., 2018). However, when it comes to educators, one study suggested that educators and teachers that utilize CT in an online setting and provide students with a suitable and healthy learning environment where each student can develop (Holmes & Packard, 2021).

Challenges of Handling Children with Special Needs During Emergency Remote Teaching

According to a study conducted by Toquero (2020), the pandemic has brought a lot of struggles and challenges, particularly to CSN, as their voices are not heard and their challenges doubled. While many teachers find online instruction productive, those foreign to it expressed immense difficulty in managing workloads and a range of other problems in managing technology, communicating with students, planning synchronous sessions, and measuring student achievements. Some teachers said they had never experienced teaching online before the emergency necessitated a switch in teaching platforms, and only a small percentage received training from their school or district (Ferri et al., 2020). Teachers acknowledged that they learned most of what they knew from each other and their research (Marshall et al., 2020). Furthermore, it was discussed that teachers have difficulty teaching children with special needs because they cannot effectively accommodate CSNs. As a result, educators rely on parents who are ill-equipped and untrained to prepare and cater to students' learning (Schuck & Lambert, 2020). Additionally, one article explained that most educators are foreign to the concept of online teaching and that it is difficult for them to learn how to teach online because they have become too accustomed to the traditional face-to-face setting (Ray, 2009). Moreover, one study explained that a teacher experiences an increase in stress, loneliness, depression, and anxiety due to being home quarantined (Toquero, 2020).

Most teachers consider the lack of adequate computer equipment alongside low internet connectivity as one of the significant barriers to successful online teaching. Teachers already faced technological problems in the traditional classroom setup, but during the pandemic, their challenges became more visible and concerning (Klapproth et al., 2020). Furthermore, an internet connection is significant for CT because teachers can use it to communicate with others (Choi & Cristol, 2018).

When it comes to the implementation of CT, Ferri et al. (2020) stated that even professionals in the implementation of CT also faced a few challenges; these are the

different perspectives and voices that needed to be heard for better outcomes in handling CSN. As methodologies and new initiatives are thrust upon CT, an increase in stress levels of CSN can be seen due to their unfamiliarity with the changes and their failure to adopt and adapt beliefs, values, and cultures; thus, professionals propose different accommodations and modifications that may suit the condition of the students. Moreover, possible conflicts between educators might arise regarding the utilization of the CT due to aspects such as power differentials, accountability regarding the partnership, and different perspectives and priorities (Goddard et al., 2007).

In addition, a lack of confidence can be a barrier to the process of CT. For CT to flourish, teachers must possess confidence in their capabilities to implement CT (Chapple, 2009). Additionally, the unwillingness of fellow teachers to collaborate with other teachers makes collaborations null and void, and educators are averse to sharing their ideas and insights (Deluca et al., 2017). Furthermore, some educators do not prefer to collaborate due to pedagogical methods, beliefs, and personalities (Bevan & Bascope, 2017). Moreover, limitations in schedules and time constraints make it difficult for CT to be implemented, wherein teachers feel isolated when they are not provided with appropriate time to plan and implement CT (Snyder & Bae, 2017). Due to time constraints, pre-arranging and organizing learning networks probably would not be plausible during ERT.

Organizations can consider organizing learning networks by assessing their faculty inclinations, previous work, and commitments to guarantee the homogeneity of learning networks (Soto et al., 2019). Furthermore, training plays a significant role in CT, wherein teachers who receive insufficient training in CT create confusion among teachers with regard to their roles, and without proper training, CT cannot flourish (Chapple, 2009). In addition, lack of training and extensive knowledge about CT have greatly affected educators in implementing it (Brendle et al., 2017).

Opportunities for Handling Children with Special Needs During Emergency Remote Teaching

In one study, it was highlighted that the pandemic opens many opportunities for children to grow, be flexible, and have exceptional growth and improvement (Toquero, 2021). The same study suggests that CSNs can benefit from enhanced communication, homeschooling, parental engagement, psychological safety, and empathy in language to help them continue their educational pursuits despite the emergency (Toquero, 2021). Furthermore, during emergency remote teaching, the online class might ease communication between the teachers and the students when it aids interactive classroom instruction (Jili et al., 2021). Additionally, emergency remote teaching could lead to a more inclusive classroom, and ERT benefits students by allowing them to have access to universal learning design (UDL) approaches. It prompts the students to become independent (Murphy, 2021).

Furthermore, with the emergence of social network technology, more opportunities for online collaboration have become available. This means that educators have a great responsibility and duty to guarantee that all students, on-campus or off-campus, have chances to improve both their academic and general abilities (Weaver et al., 2010). Moreover, one article suggested that collaboration between Gen Ed and SpEd teachers regarding virtual reality technology can enhance their instruction in teaching students with special needs (Wertzberger, 2019). Other advantages of virtual reality in education

include the capacity to encourage students' creativity and spark their imaginations and deliver immersive learning experiences. This may encourage them to pursue new intellectual pursuits (Hicks, 2021). In addition, the lack of or decreased budget can inhibit the teacher's capabilities to collaborate; providing teachers with more budget can enhance their planning in collaborating with others (Edenfield, 2013).

Methodology

Participants

The purposive sampling method was utilized in this study. Purposive sampling is a sampling technique where researchers utilize their judgment in selecting the informants for a study and in building a sample that meets the goals of the study (Cohen et al., 2007). In this study, the researchers utilized their knowledge about the concepts of SpEd and utilized it to select the study participants, which consisted of Gen Ed and SpEd teachers. The criteria for selecting suitable informants consist of the following: (a) has a background or history of handling CSN; (b) teaches in a public institution that has SpEd programs, and; (c) has taught for at least three years. The reason why the participants of this study must have at least three years of experience is that in one study, it was explained that teachers who have been teaching for three years or less indicated that they are either mildly prepared or ill-prepared for teaching or handling students (Cleveland, 2008); therefore, experienced teachers who have been teaching for three years or longer have more experience in handling CSNs. In addition, most SpEd teachers work in public institutions (Henke et al., 1996), which is why this study limits its scope to public schools.

Instrument

This study collected data using semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions. Semi-structured interviews were used in this study because they are suited to gathering the opinions and perceptions of the respondents about a specific phenomenon or issue. Interviews allow the researcher to explore topics in-depth (While & Barriball, 1994), which makes them suitable for this study since the goal is to examine both Gen Ed and SpEd teachers' experiences in using CT, the phenomenon in this study, in handling CSN during the ERT. The study utilized these techniques to gather data because the research is centered on the experiences, particularly the challenges and opportunities, of both Gen Ed and SpEd teachers in utilizing CT when handling children with special needs during the ERT.

The first technique utilized is the interview, which is composed of different types of questions: closed-ended questions and open-ended questions. The first few questions are closed-ended because they aim to identify the specific information needed regarding the participant's background. The succeeding questions are open-ended questions; they allowed the participant to answer the questions based on their own experiences, views, and values. The second data gathering technique utilized is the focus group discussion. It is an approach that aims to gather the different points of view of the participants in the same setting. It provides credible data from a specific population.

The researchers decided to utilize two forms data collection in order to triangulate data. Data triangulation is necessary in qualitative phenomenological research since it can significantly aid the researchers in gaining an extensive understanding of the

phenomenon by using multiple methods of gathering data (Patton, 1990).

Procedure

Two ways of gathering data were utilized in this study since the study is a qualitative phenomenological research centered on the perceptions, challenges, and opportunities Gen Ed and SpEd teachers have experienced when using CT in handling CSN during the ERT.

The study used Google Forms to preselect the participants using social media platforms. Letters of consent were sent to the school division administrator. The next step was sending letters of invitation and consent forms to the participants. If the participant consented to participate in the study, the researchers scheduled a one-on-one interview with them via an online app such as Zoom. Face-to-face semi-structured interviews were conducted if the participants preferred it. Furthermore, before administering the interview and the focus group discussion, the researchers asked the participants' consent to have the interview recorded.

A similar procedure occurred during the focus group discussion. However, the researchers modified the number of participants to five per online focus group discussion. The participants were divided into five groups, with each consisting of one Gen Ed teacher and two SpEd teachers. The focus group discussions were conducted for five days.

Data Analysis

The data from both interviews and focus group discussions were analyzed using thematic analysis, an approach that organizes and examines qualitative data through various forms of analysis (Nowell et al., 2017). Thematic analysis was done to identify patterns in the data concerning the challenges and opportunities of Gen Ed and SpEd teachers when employing CT in handling CSN during the ERT.

Additionally, thematic analysis was conducted through a series of coding where the data from the transcribed interviews and focus group discussion were organized and categorized depending on the information the participants provided. Three coding processes were conducted, which are pre-coding (open coding), first-cycle coding (axial coding), and second-cycle coding (substantial coding). During pre-coding, a set of codes was used to categorize data from the participant responses (Saldana, 2016).

The first cycle of coding (axial coding) is a process that analyzes the categorized codes in textual form to provide an outline of the study (Andrasik et al., 2014). Then the second cycle of coding (actual coding) was utilized wherein the categorized codes were to present an overview of the codes and data. The method allows researchers to analyze patterns of codes to determine which ones are relevant to the study.

Thematic coding was done to come up with themes that correspond to the perceptions, challenges, and opportunities experienced by General and Special Education teachers in using CT with CSNs during the ERT. Thematic coding was done to come up with themes that correspond to the perceptions, challenges, and opportunities experienced by General and Special Education teachers in using CT with CSNs during the ERT.

Result and Analysis

During the ERT, GedEd and SpEd teachers had different perceptions, challenges, and opportunities using CT in handling CSNs. The study sought to explore these using semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions.

Perceptions of General Education and Special Education Teachers in Collaborative Teaching Team

Teaching (Working Together)

During the interviews and focus group discussions, *team teaching* was one of the most frequent responses given by the participants.

Collaboration is an approach that allows two or more educators and specialists to come together to contribute individual skills to develop a mutual understanding of expertise (Mofield, 2020). According to the participants, this theme validates the following response:

P13: "Collaborative teaching is team teaching [...] nagtutulong-tulong kami para doon sa bata [...] teamwork."

This indicates that CT is effective in the following areas: teaching design, evaluation of performance, brainstorming strategies, structured classification of subject data, individualized learning procedures, research and development teams, and appropriate methods of discussion (Harati, 2012).

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Challenges of General Education and Special Education Teachers in Collaborative Teaching

Internet Connection (Unstable Internet Connection)

Shifting from traditional face-to-face setting to ERT, internet connection greatly affected the planning, collaboration, and communication of GenEd and SpEd teachers handling CSN. Ferri et al. (2020) stated that ERT could bring challenges that can affect the educational models of the students in utilizing technology for their learning processes. In particular, technological challenges, pedagogical challenges, and social challenges can become a challenge for both the student and the teacher. According to the participants, the following statements highlight the challenges they experienced regarding internet connection:

P2: "[...] internet connection. Kaya naapektuhan din yung communication between regular teachers sa pagcreate ng better plan para sa mga bata. Madalas hindi kami nakakapagcollaborate ng maayos."

This validates the claim that successful CT, planning, and communication between GenEd and SpEd teachers depend on stable internet connections.

Lack of Confidence and Unwillingness (Hesitant)

The results show that most teachers are not confident in handling CSN. Some hesitated to utilize CT during ERT. In addition, lack of confidence can be a barrier to CT; for it to flourish, teachers must possess the capabilities to implement CT (Chapple, 2019). Participants explain that while CT is available, some are unwilling to apply it:

P5: "[...] some teachers are unwilling to help special children; most are hesitant."

Documented accounts stated that lack of confidence and unwillingness is challenging for GenEd and SpEd teachers in handling CSN during ERT. This certifies that despite utilizing CT, most teachers lack confidence in handling CSN due to hesitation

Time Constraints (Conflicts of Schedule)

In CT, the importance of time is always highlighted, especially in teaching and making lesson plans and in scheduling a common time for educators to collaborate. Moreover, schedule conflicts and time constraints make it difficult for CT to be implemented; teachers feel isolated when they are not provided with appropriate time to plan and implement CT (Snyder and Bay, 2017). Participants stated that one of their dilemmas is limited time in CT:

P4: "[...] she's not present (GenEd Teacher) or maybe hindi kame nagtutugma ng time."

The accounts stated that limited time in CT, such as appropriate time and conflict of schedule to work together brought by the ERT when handling CSN, is considered a challenge that hinders CT.

Inadequate Support (Training, Information, Communication, Promotion)

Due to differences in teachers' experiences, *inadequate support* emerged. Teachers expressed receiving inadequate support in CT training; they also did not feel that there was adequate information about it. The promotion of CT was also affected by inaccessible resources. Training plays a significant part in CT since teachers who receive insufficient CT training creates confusion among teachers regarding their roles; without proper training, CT cannot flourish (Chapple, 2009). According to the participants, there was limited information and communication regarding CT; it was not promoted well either:

Due to differences in teachers' experiences, *inadequate support* emerged. Teachers expressed receiving inadequate support in CT training; they also did not feel that there was adequate information about it. The promotion of CT was also affected by inaccessible resources. Training plays a significant part in CT since teachers who receive insufficient CT training creates confusion among teachers regarding their roles; without proper training, CT cannot flourish (Chapple, 2009). According to the participants, there was limited information and communication regarding CT; it was not promoted well either:

P5: "[...] lack of training, orientation, and information."

Opportunities for General Education and Special Education Teachers in Collaborative Teaching

Communication (Effective Communication)

In CT, communication between teachers and parents is important as it builds and establishes their relationship; this, in turn, allows teachers to understand their students better. Toquero (2021) stated in one study that CSNs can benefit from measures such as enhanced communication and empathy in language to help them continue their educational pursuits despite the emergency:

P8: "Constant communication with supportive co-teachers and parents [...] and a better understanding of the pupils' needs."

The accounts stated above claim that communication establishes a better relationship between teachers and parents, which allows them to understand the needs of CSNs better.

Teaching Strategies (Instructional Methods, Teachers Role)

To cope with the challenges brought by the sudden changes in handling CSN during the ERT, the participants discussed their experiences in overcoming different hurdles regarding CT, specifically their teaching strategy. One study reveals that teaching future educators about CT can prepare them to handle children with CSN and enhance their way of instructing CSN because it eliminates competition and isolation and promotes a healthy relationship between SpEd and GenEd teachers (Rabin, 2019). According to the participants, the following statements prove their understanding of the connection between teaching strategies and CT:

P6: "It makes me think out beyond the box, to strategize from a new perspective [...] understanding of the roles we play in these kids' lives."

These accounts indicate that various teaching strategies, including thinking out of the norm, learning other teaching strategies, and duplicating teaching strategies are beneficial to support CT and give way to mechanisms that are beneficial in handling CSNs during the ERT.

Training (Seminar and Workshop)

CT requires teachers to have sufficient knowledge and skills in handling CSNs during the ERT. Parriera (2015) stated that understanding GenEd teachers' training, perspectives, and perceptions of competence in dealing with children with diverse needs is crucial to their success:

P3: "[...] dumadaan sila (GenEd Teachers) sa mga trainings namin at natutuwa din yung mga teachers kasi kinakailangan din namin ng mga partners na receiving teachers."

The account stated above claim that trainings for teachers, such as seminars and workshops, improve teacher relationships as they gain knowledge in handling CSNs during the ERT. Additionally, training can help teachers gain new knowledge about handling CSNs.

Budget (Funding)

Due to the drastic need for instructional materials during the ERT, funding has been

identified as one of the ways to continue providing quality education to CSNs. Providing teachers with more budget can enhance planning when collaborating with others (Edenfield, 2013). Participants stated that funds could be used to prepare instructional materials for CSNs.

P5: "[...] "given a sufficient budget to prepare the materials, I was able to laminate (instructional materials)."

The account mentioned that given sufficient budget, the teacher was able to provide instructional materials for CSNs during the ERT.

Technology (Navigating Applications)

In the current pandemic situation, technology has been extremely useful in CT. During the ERT, teachers were provided with a plethora of methods to enhance CT where they can utilize platforms such as Messenger, Microsoft Teams, Google Meet, and Zoom (Barron et al., 2021). Participants mentioned that sharing knowledge on how to navigate different applications made it convenient to communicate during the ERT:

P10: "We share different knowledge [...] how to navigate the different applications in teaching such as Zoom."

The account mentioned the convenience and the relevance of utilizing technologies during the ERT. This includes knowledge on utilizing various technologies and applications for handling CSN during the ERT.

Discussion

The definitions of CT vary greatly. In this study, CT is referred to as a practice where teachers work together to achieve a common goal. Mofield (2020) expressed that CT is an approach that allows two or more individual educators and specialists to come together and work together in contributing skills to develop a better understanding of their field of expertise.

The definitions of CT vary greatly. In this study, CT is referred to as a practice where teachers work together to achieve a common goal. Mofield (2020) expressed that CT is an approach that allows two or more individual educators and specialists to come together and work together in contributing skills to develop a better understanding of their field of expertise.

One of the most prevalent challenges in using CT in handling CSNs during the ERT are technical problems such as unstable internet connection and power interruptions (Klapproth et al., 2020). Most of the respondents expressed similar concerns when interviewed. Furthermore, an internet connection is crucial to CT because it can be utilized by teachers to communicate with other people (Choi & Cristol, 2018). Another emerging challenge is teachers' unwillingness and lack of confidence about CT; unwillingness is one of the reasons why CT becomes a challenge for teachers in handling CSN during the ERT (Chapple, 2019). Additionally, the unwillingness of teachers to collaborate with each other makes collaborations pointless since educators are averse to sharing their ideas and insights with each other (Deluca et al., 2017). Furthermore, some educators do not prefer to collaborate due to differences in pedagogical methods, beliefs, and personalities

(Bevan and Bascope, 2017).

Moreover, conflicts in schedule and time constraints also provide challenges for teachers to implement CT when handling CSNs during the ERT (Synder & Bay, 2017). In addition, pre-arranging and organizing learning networks probably would not be plausible during the ERT because of time constraints. However, organizations can still consider organizing learning networks by assessing their faculty inclinations, previous work, and commitments to guarantee the homogeneity of learning networks (Soto et al., 2019). Another common challenge for educators in employing CT is inadequate support, such as lack of training, information, communication, and promotion, factors that can hinder the implementation and use of CT in handling CSNs during the ERT (Chapple, 2009). The participants expressed that even if the use of CT is accessible, it is not widely promoted; some lack awareness while most lack training, contributing to confusion about the distribution of roles among the teachers (Chapple, 2009). Moreover, the lack of extensive knowledge regarding CT has greatly affected educators' capacity to implement CT due to their lack of training (Brendle et al., 2017).

On the other hand, some opportunities emerged from using CT in handling CSNs during the ERT. One opportunity that the participants experienced was enhanced communication, which became an opportunity for teachers to properly employ CT in handling CSN during ERT (Toquero, 2021). The participants validated that they continuously communicated with the GenEd teachers, resulting in a better understanding of handling CSN during ERT. Another coping mechanism that the teachers experienced in using CT is that it provided them with a variety of teaching strategies, such as improved instructional methods and proper distribution of teacher roles as well as providing the educators the opportunity to share knowledge about their instructional methods, reflect on their teaching strategies and eliminate the sense of competition among them (Rabin, 2019). Moreover, receiving training became an opportunity for the teachers to gain knowledge and skills as they collaborated with other teachers in handling CSNs during the ERT (Parriera, 2015). The participants claimed that after training, the teachers who participated in it were able to learn new skills; they were also able to share their experiences. In addition, a study stated that utilizing Twitter and Facebook in educational gatherings made participants' experiences worthwhile and enhanced their professional growth (Spilker et al., 2020).

Another opportunity that emerged is that increased financial aid made it easier to employ CT during ERT since a bigger budget can enhance CT planning (Edenfield, 2013). In addition, budget constraints can be a hindrance to educators and in implementin and planning CT (Abdi, 2015). Nevertheless, technology is also one of the opportunities teachers could use to to properly utilize CT in handling CSNs during the ERT (Barron et al., 2021). The participants stated that through technology, teachers were able to share their knowledge in utilizing technologies. Technology is also a popular medium for teachers and parents to communicate and learn during ERT, since appropriate technologies can facilitate and enhance the educator's capacity to implement CT (Boyd, 2007).

Conclusion

The CT approach, indeed, can be a beneficial approach that can be utilized to handle CSNs while meeting their needs (Daniels, 2017). The use of CT provides teachers with the following benefits: enhanced productivity, professional development, increased sense of responsibility, learning opportunities, reduced workload, and opportunities to reflect and redesign instructional methods (Hargreaves, 1994).

On the other hand, emerging challenges are unstable internet connection (Klapproth et al.,

2020), lack of willingness and confidence in the teachers' capabilities (Chapple, 2009), conflict in schedule and time constraints (Snyder & Bay, 2017), inadequate support such as lack of training, information, and promotion of CT (Chapple, 2009). Some of the opportunities that arose during the ERT are constant communication (Toquero, 2020), provision and sharing of teaching strategies and proper distribution of teacher roles (Rabin, 2019), provision of training programs (Parriera, 2015), increased budget in planning (Edenfield, 2013), and provision of various technologies such as devices and applications.

The purpose of this paper is to explore the experiences of both Gen Ed and SpEd teachers, more specifically, the perceptions, challenges, and opportunities they encountered in using CT in handling CSNs during the ERT. This is to fill the knowledge gap that revolves around the concept of CT and how it was applied during the ERT. Moreover, this paper provides findings and data regarding the perceptions, challenges, and opportunities of Gen Ed and SpEd teachers, and the data from this research can be utilized in future scenarios should ERT occur again.

The paper affirms that teachers, the primary implementers of the school curriculum, face colossal challenges when significant curricular changes are implemented. However, in exploring the challenges they encountered and the mechanisms they explored to achieve their academic goals during a crisis, important information that can help improve the training and development of teachers emerged. The difficulties that challenge Special Education and General Education teachers in supporting learners with special needs overlap. The findings of the study juxtaposed with the literature provide insights to better handle children with special needs should a crisis hit education again.

Recommendations

The following statements are essential for future researchers who will conduct similar studies and who may use the results of this study as reference for future studies.

- There is a need to enhance teachers' skills to help them become more adept at what they do. History has taught us that a pandemic can hit anytime; when it does, the educational system will be disrupted once again. The Philippines is a disaster-prone country, and disaster can come in other forms, not just a deadly virus. Therefore, there is a need to proactively draft and implement policies that will help teachers become more equipped and competent in implementing the school curricula. It is important to note that competence will not only be centered on content and pedagogies but in other mechanisms that help attain educational goals, collaboration, for instance.
- The researchers recommend that future researchers examine the effects of using CT during the ERT among parents. The proponents of this paper recommend that future researchers who will be studying this concept explore the effects of using CT during the ERT through the lens of the parents. The researchers also recommend including other respondents such as the school administration or staff gather further data about CT during the ERT. This also includes the principal, guidance counselor, and the other professionals contributing to the learning journey of the CSNs. This study also recommends looking into the effectiveness of CT after the pandemic when adjustments occur in the modes of teaching. The focus is to elaborate on CT's effectiveness in handling CSNs. To further expound on the study, the researchers recommend exploring GenEd and SpEd teachers' perceptions, challenges, and opportunities while using CT in handling CSNs during online classes.

References

- Abdi, E. (2015). The Effects of Reducing School Budgets and Approaches to Proceed toward Successful Educational Programs in Era of Budget Disparity with Concentrating on New Jersey Public Education. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283521285>
- Achinstein, B. (2001, November 30). Conflict amid community: The micropolitics of teacher Collaboration., teachers college record, 2002. ERIC. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ649782>
- Andrasik, M., Frey, S., & Endeshaw, M. (2014). Qualitative methods: Coding & data analysis [Slides]. OSP
- Avalos-Bevan, B., & Bascope, M. (2017, October). Teacher Informal Collaboration for Professional Improvement: Beliefs, Contexts, and Experience. Teacher Informal Collaboration for Professional Improvement: Beliefs, Contexts, and Experience, 2017.
- Barron, T. (2021, July 23). Co-Teaching in Uncertain Times: Using Technology to Improve Student Learning and Manage Today's Complex Educational Landscape. Journals of Special doi/abs/10.1177/01626434211033579
- Boyd, D. (2017). Social Network Sites: Public, Private, or What? Social Network Sites: Public, Private, or What? <http://www.danah.org/papers/KnowledgeTree.pdf>
- Brendle, J. (2017). A study of Co-Teaching identifying effective implementation strategies. *International Journal of Special Education*, 32(3), 538–550.
- Burns, D., & Bae, S. (2017). The Kids Benefit From It, So It's Worth It": Time for Teaching and Learning at SMASH (1st ed., Vol. 1). Stanford Center for Opportunity Policy in Education. <https://edpolicy.stanford.edu/sites/default/files/SMASH%20Final.pdf>
- Cahapay, M. B., & Rotas, E. E. (2020). Difficulties in remote learning: Voices of philippine university students in the wake of COVID-19 crisis. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(2), 147–158. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4299835>
- Chan, C. K. K., & Fai Pang, M. (2006). Teacher collaboration in learning communities. *Teaching Education*, 17(1), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10476210500527899>
- Chapple, J. M. (2009a). CO-TEACHING: FROM OBSTACLES TO OPPORTUNITIES (1st ed., Vol. 1). Ashland University ProQuest Dissertations Publishing.
- Chapple, J. M. (2009b). CO-TEACHING: FROM OBSTACLES TO OPPORTUNITIES. Ashland University ProQuest Dissertations Publishing.
- Choi, M., Cristol, D., & Gimbert, B. (2018). Teachers as digital citizens: The influence of individual backgrounds, internet use and psychological characteristics on teachers' levels of digital citizenship. *Computers & Education*, 121, 143–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2018.03.005>
- Clement, M., & Vandenberghe, R. (2000). Teachers' professional development: A solitary or collegial (ad)venture? *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 16(1), 81–101.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0742-051x\(99\)00051-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0742-051x(99)00051-7)

- Cleveland, R. (2008). New teachers perceptions on their preparation. *School Works at WMU*, 1–93.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2007). *Research methods in education* (6th ed.). Routledge.
- Coughlin, S. L. (2017). Collaborative practices among professionals in special education workplace. University of New Hampshire.
- Cresswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Daniels, O. J. (2017). A case study of collaboration between general education teachers and special education teachers in a southern rural high school. Nova Southeastern University.
- Després-Bedward, T., Avery, L., & Phirangee, K. (2018). Student perspectives on the role of the instructor in Face-to-Face and online learning. *International Journal of Information and Education Tehnology*, 8(10), 706–712. <https://doi.org/10.18178/ijiet.2018.8.10.1126>
- Drucker, P. F. (1999). The new pluralism. *Leader to Leader*, 1999(14), 18–23. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ltl.40619991405>
- Edenfield, B. D. (2013). Teacher Perceptions of the Impact of Reduced School Budgets on Their Ability to Meet Instructional Needs of Their Students. *Digital Commons@Georgia Southern*.
- Ferri, F., Grifoni, P., & Guzzo, T. (2020). Online learning and emergency remote Teaching: Opportunities and challenges in Emergency situations. *Societies*, 10(86), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc10040086>
- Flores, L. M. (2020). Teaching students with disabilities in the inclusive classrooms: Fostering collaboration between specialists and nonspecialists. University of Houston.
- Fulton, K. (2003). Redesigning schools to meet 21st century learning needs. *ERIC*, 30(9), 30–36.
- Goddard, Y. L., Goddard, R. D., & Tschannen-Moran, M. (2007). A theoretical and empirical investigation of teacher collaboration for school improvement and student achievement in public elementary schools. *Teachers College Record*, 109(4), 877–896.
- Harati, R. (2012). Collaboration teaching and its role on education performance and students achievement. *European Journal of Experimental Biology*, 2(6), 2182–2187.
- Hargreaves, A. (1994). *Changing teachers, changing times: Teachers' work and culture in the postmodern Age* London: Cassell. (Reprinted ed.) [E-book]. British Library Cataloguing.
- Henke, R., Choy, S., & Geis, S. (1996). *Schools and staffing in the united states: A statistic profile* (Vols. 96–124). MPR Associates, Inc.
- Hicks, P. (2021, May 12). The pros and cons of using virtual reality in the classroom. *eLearning Industry*. <https://elearningindustry.com/pros-cons-using-virtual->

reality-in-the-classroom

- Hiller, J. (2019). Finding their voice: Co-Teaching, communication, and collaboration. University of Michigan-Dearborn.
- Holmes, G. A., & Packard, A. L. (2021). An instructional Problem-Solving collaboration between two university professors. University of West Georgia, 93–97. Jili, N. N., Ede, C. I., & Masuku, M. M. (2021). Emergency remote teaching in higher education during covid-19: Challenges and opportunities. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 10(5), 1. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v10n5p1>
- John - Steiner, V. (1992). Creative lives, creative tensions. *Creativity Research Journal*, 5(1), 99–108. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10400419209534426>
- John-Steiner, V., Weber, R. J., & Minnis, M. (1998). The challenge of studying collaboration. *American Educational Research Journal*, 35(4), 773–783. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00028312035004773>
- Klapproth, F., Federkeil, L., Heinschke, F., & Jungmann, T. (2020). Teachers experiences of stress and their coping strategies during COVID - 19 induced distance teaching. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 4(4), 444–452. <https://doi.org/10.33902/jpr.2020062805>
- Kramer, R., & Gray, B. (1989). Collaborating: Finding common ground for multiparty problems. *The Academy of Management Review*, 15(3), 545–547. <https://doi.org/10.2307/258026>
- Lange, D. (2021). COVID and the classroom: The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on special education and policy implementation. Honors Theses.
- Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. S. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. SAGE Publications.
- Louise Barriball, K., & While, A. (1994). Collecting data using a semi-structured interview: A discussion paper. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 19(2), 328–335. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2648.1994.tb01088.x>
- Marshall, D. T., Shannon, D. M., & Love, S. M. (2020). How teachers experienced the COVID-19 transition to remote instruction. *SAGE Journals*, 102(3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0031721720970702>
- Misirli, O., & Ergulec, F. (2021). Emergency remote teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic: Parents experiences and perspectives. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(6), 6699–6718. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10520-4>
- Mofield, E. L. (2020). Benefits and barriers to collaboration and Co-Teaching. *SAGE Journals*, 20–33. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1076217519880588Articleinformation>
- Moran, S., & John - Steiner, V. (2003). *Creativity in the making*. Oxford Scholarship Online. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195149005.003.0003>
- Murphy, R. (2021). Higher education students with disabilities' perceptions of emergency remote learning – exploring the benefits and barriers of e-learning. *AHEAD*.
- Nabi, S. (2020). Effectiveness of online education over traditional education system during COVID 19 –an analysis. *Psychology and Education Journal*, 57(9), 4012–4019. <https://doi.org/10.17762/pae.v57i9.1619>
- Nowell, L. S., Norris, J. M., White, D. E., & Moules, N. J. (2017). *Thematic analysis*.

- International Journal of Qualitative Methods, 16(1), 160940691773384.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406917733847>
- Patton, M. Q. (1999). Enhancing the quality and credibility of qualitative analysis. *NCBI*, 34, 1189–1208.
- Rabin, C. (2019). Co-Teaching: Collaborative and caring teacher preparation. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 71(1), 135–147. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487119872696>
- Rannastu, M. (2020). Challenges for distance learning and online collaboration in the time of COVID-19: Interviews with science teachers. *Collaboration Technologies and Social Computing*, 12324, 128–142. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58157-2_9
- Rao, Z., & Chen, H. (2019). Teachers' perceptions of difficulties in team teaching between local- and native-English-speaking teachers in EFL teaching. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 41(4), 333–347. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01434632.2019.1620753>
- Ray, J. (2009). Faculty perspective: Training and course development for the online classroom. *MERLOT Journal of Online Learning and Teaching*, 5(2).
- Ricci, L. A., & Fingon, J. C. (2017). Faculty modeling Co-Teaching and collaboration practices in general education and special education courses in teacher preparation programmes. *Athens Journal of Education*, 4(4), 351–362. <https://doi.org/10.30958/aje.4-4-4>
- Saldana, J. (2016). Decoding Coding via The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers by Johnny Saldaña. *The Qualitative Report*. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2009.2856>
- Schuck, R. K., & Lambert, R. (2020). “Am i doing enough?” special educators' experiences with emergency remote teaching in spring 2020. *Education Science*, 10(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci10110320>
- Soto, M., Gupta, D., Dick, L., & Appelgate, M. (2019). Bridging Distance: Professional Development for Higher Education Faculty Through Technology-Facilitated Lesson Study. *Journal of University Teaching and Learning Practice*, 16(3), 93–112. <https://doi.org/10.53761/1.16.3>.
- Spilker, M., Prinsen, F., & Kalz, M. (2019). Valuing technology-enhanced academic conferences for continuing professional development. A systematic literature review. *Professional Development in Education*, 46(3), 482–499. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19415257.2019.162961>
- Toquero, C. M. (2020a). Emergency remote teaching amid COVID-19: The turning point. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(1), 185–188. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.388174>
- Toquero, C. M. (2020b). Inclusion of people with disabilities amid COVID-19: Laws, interventions, recommendations. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Educational Research*, 10(2), 158–177. <https://doi.org/10.17583/remie.2020.5877>
- Weaver, D., Viper, S., Latter, J., & McIntosh, P. C. (2010). Off campus students' experiences collaborating online, using wikis. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 26(6), 847–860. <https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.1046>
- Wertzberger, E. (2019). The future of field experiences in distance education: A case study

of co-teaching practices in a Telepresence-Facilitated field placement. *Theory & Practice in Rural Education*, 9(2), 35–46. <https://doi.org/10.3776/tpre.201>